

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDY OF THE As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 SYSTEM AND THE ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SOLID SOLUTION ALLOYS

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Abstract

The As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 systems were studied using physicochemical analysis methods: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as density and microhardness determination. A T-x phase diagram was constructed. It was established that the phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system is quasi-binary and eutectic. The As_2Te_3 and TlGaS_2 compounds form a eutectic with a composition of 15 mol. % TlGaS_2 and a temperature of 280°C. It was found that in the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on the As_2Te_3 compound reach 4 mol. % TlGaS_2 , while solid solutions based on the TlGaS_2 compound reach 6 mol. % As_2Te_3 . The temperature dependences of the electrical conductivity and thermo-EMF of $(\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3)_{1-x}(\text{TlGaS}_2)_x$ solid solution alloys ($x=0.01; 0.02; 0.04$) were studied.

Keywords: system, phase, eutectic, microhardness, density.

Introduction

Arsenic chalcogenides As_2X_3 ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{Te}$) and alloys based on them exhibit photovoltaic [1-4] and luminescent [5] properties and are widely used in electronics. Semiconductor fibers based on arsenic chalcogenides are currently being extensively studied [6-8]. Unlike arsenic sulfide and selenide compounds, arsenic telluride forms in crystalline form under normal conditions. The compound As_2Te_3 , as well as new phases and solid solutions based on it, are materials with photovoltaic and thermoelectric properties [9-11]. The compound As_2Te_3 forms in a crystalline state under normal conditions. Ternary and quaternary compounds obtained in systems consisting of thallium chalcogenides are glassy and form extensive glass transition regions. Therefore, studying the interaction of As_2Te_3 and TlGaS_2 is of scientific and practical importance.

We previously studied the chemical interaction of arsenic sulfide and selenide compounds with ternary thallium compounds [12-14]. The As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system is studied for the first time.

The aim of this work is a physicochemical study of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system and an investigation of the electrical properties of the obtained alloys (solid solutions).

The As_2Te_3 compound melts with an open maximum at 381°C and crystallizes in a monoclinic syngony with the lattice parameters: $a = 14.339 \text{ \AA}$; $b = 4.006 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 9.873 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 95^\circ$, sp. gr. C2/m [15]. The TlGaS_2 compound melts congruently at 905°C and crystallizes in a tetragonal syngony with the unit cell parameters: $a = 7.29$; $c = 29.90 \text{ \AA}$, $z = 16$, the density and microhardness $\rho = 5.64 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and 700 MPa, respectively [16].

Experimental Section

As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 alloys were synthesized from As_2Se_3 and TlGaS_2 components in quartz ampoules evacuated to 0.133 Pa at temperatures of 500–1000°C.

To achieve equilibrium, the alloys were annealed at 280°C for 300 h.

Equilibrium alloys of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system were studied using physicochemical analysis methods: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as microhardness and density measurements.

DTA of the alloys was performed on a TERMOSCAN-2 instrument at a heating rate of 5°C/min. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed on a D2 PHASER instrument using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a Ni filter. The microhardness of the system's alloys was examined using an MIM-8 microscope on pre-etched sections polished with GOI paste. The microhardness of the system's alloys was measured using a PMT-3 microhardness tester. The density of the system's alloys was determined using the pycnometric method using toluene as a filler.

Results and discussion

All As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system alloys are stable to air, water, and organic solvents. As_2Te_3 -rich alloys dissolve well in concentrated mineral acids HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 . Equilibrium alloys were studied using physicochemical analysis.

The results of differential thermal analysis of the alloys of the system showed that the thermograms of the alloys exhibit two temperature effects associated with the solidus and liquidus.

To study the phase composition of the As_2Te_3 - TlGaS_2 system alloys, a microstructural analysis was performed. The microstructure of alloys containing 15, 50, and 94 mol. % TlGaS_2 is shown in Fig. 1 a, b, c. The alloy with 15 mol. % TlGaS_2 indicates eutectic compositions. The alloy with 50 mol. % TlGaS_2 belongs to the two-phase part of the system. Single-phase alloys with a composition of 94 mol. % TlGaS_2 are solid solutions based on the compound TlGaS_2 .

Fig. 1. Microstructures of alloys of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system. - 15 mol. %, b) - 50 mol. %, c) - 94 mol. $TlGaS_2$.

An X-ray diffraction analysis of alloys containing 15, 50, and 94 mol.% $TlGaS_2$ was performed (Fig. 2). As can be seen from Fig. 2, the diffraction patterns of the alloys containing 15 and 50 mol. % $TlGaS_2$ contain diffraction lines consisting of lines of the original components. These alloys are two-phase. The sample con-

taining 94 mol. % $TlGaS_2$ is single-phase and represents a solid solution based on $TlGaS_2$. Thus, X-ray diffraction analysis confirms the results of DTA and MSA.

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system. 1- As_2Te_3 , 2-15, 3-50, 4-94, 5-100 mol. % $TlGaS_2$

Fig. 3. T - x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system.

Based on the physicochemical data, a T-x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system was constructed (Fig. 3). It was established that the phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system belongs to the quasi-binary eutectic type. The compounds As_2Se_3 and $TlGaS_2$ form a eutectic, the composition of which reaches 15 mol. % $TlGaS_2$ and a temperature of 280°C. In the system at room temperature, the content of solid solutions based

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of solid solution alloys $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$. 1-1 mol. %, 2-2 mol. %, 3-4 mol. % $TlGaS_2$.

The temperature dependence of electrical conductivity and thermo-EMF were studied on single-crystal samples of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$ ($x=0.01; 0.02; 0.04$) solid solutions in the temperature range of 300-600 K. The temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$ ($x=0.01; 0.02; 0.04$) solid solutions is shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen from Fig. 4, the electrical conductivity value increases over the entire temperature range, which is typical for semiconductors. The $f-10^3/T, K$ dependence curves can be divided into two temperature ranges: 300-450 K and 450-600 K. The first value of electrical conductivity corresponds to the impurity conductivity region of 300-450 K, and the second to the intrinsic conductivity region of 450-600 K (Fig. 4). The temperature dependence of the thermo-EMF of the $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$ ($x=0.01; 0.02; 0.04$) solid solution alloys is shown in Fig. 5. Alloys containing 1, 2, and 4 mol. % $TlGaS_2$ have maximum values at 450 K. With a further increase in temperature, they gradually decrease. Depending on the composition, the thermoelectromotive force increases.

Conclusion

Using physicochemical analysis, a T-x phase diagram for the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system was constructed. The phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaS_2$ system was found to be quasi-binary and eutectic. Co-crystallization of As_2Te_3 and $TlGaS_2$ results in a binary eutectic with a composition of 15 mol. % $TlGaS_2$ and a temperature of 280°C. It was found that at room temperature, solid solutions based on the As_2Te_3 compound reach 4 mol. % $TlGaS_2$, while those based on the $TlGaS_2$ compound reach 6 mol. % As_2Te_3 . The temperature dependences of the electrical conductivity and thermoelectric power of the $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$ ($x = 0.01; 0.02; 0.04$) solid solution alloys were studied. It was established that the obtained solid solutions are low-resistance semiconductors.

on As_2Te_3 reaches 4 mol. % $TlGaS_2$, and on $TlGaS_2$, up to 6 mol. % As_2Te_3 .

The liquidus of the system consists of monovariant curves of the primary crystallization of α solid solutions based on As_2Te_3 and β solid solutions based on $TlGaS_2$. Co-crystallization of the α - and β -phases terminates at the double eutectic point. Below the solidus line, two-phase alloys ($\alpha + \beta$) crystallize.

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of thermo-EMF of solid solution alloys $(As_2Te_3)_{1-x}(TlGaS_2)_x$. 1-1 mol. %, 2-2 mol. %, 3-4 mol. % $TlGaS_2$.

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